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Innovation Action

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D1.8 – Data Management Plan

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Executive Summary

In accordance with H2020 guidelines related to data management [1], every participant project to the **pilot action on open access to research data** should develop a Data Management Plan (DMP) in which they specify what data will be open. According to these guidelines, a DMP should detail:

- What data the project will collect and generate;
- Whether, and how, this data will be exploited or shared and made accessible/open for verification and re-use;
- How this data will be curated and preserved.

In that frame, this document constitutes the Data Management Plan and strategy for the open data treatment within the HIT2GAP project. The document also specifies the data that are maintained confidential and explains why. It should be noted that this document belongs to the Work Package number 1 of the HIT2GAP project which is responsible for collecting the requirements. The overall requirements of the project are directly related to the collected data in the project that are used by data processing modules for energy saving purposes. These modules generate new data related to the energy saving and can feed energy management tools developed during the project lifespan.

This document is likely to evolve during the project lifecycle and be updated to include new data sets and new results sets.

This version of the document is the fourth version corresponding to the update expected at the end of the project (M48). It includes the refined list of data collected and generated as well as solutions for the repository of data sets selected within the HIT2GAP project. This version of the report also includes the information made available through open access in relation with the developments achieved at the end of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

In Horizon 2020, a limited and flexible pilot action on open access to research data is currently implemented. In accordance with H2020 guidelines related to data management [1], every participant to the **pilot action on open access to research data** should develop a Data Management Plan (DMP) in which he/she specifies:

- What data the project will collect and generate;
- Whether and how this data will be exploited or shared and made accessible/open for verification and re-use, and;
- How this data will be curated and preserved.

At the proposal stage, the HIT2GAP consortium decided to participate in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020 on a voluntary basis. In that frame, the deliverable D1.8 provides the main requirements concerning the open access data and explains how this requirement is addressed in the HIT2GAP project.

As specified in the guidelines, a DMP describes the data management life cycle for all data sets that are collected, processed or generated by the research project. It is a document outlining how research data will be handled during a research project, and even after the project is completed, describing what data will be collected, processed or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

It should be noted that this document is also closely related to the ethical issues management plan that also requires some technical restrictions associated to the security of personal data that will be collected in the pilot sites. Moreover, this DMP is consistent with the exploitation and protection of results that has been developed as part of the HIT2GAP project.

In order to elaborate the DMP, the checklist proposed by the Digital Curation Centre (DCC¹) in the UK has been considered, with key questions as follows:

1. What data will you collect or create?
2. How will the data be collected or created?
3. What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?
4. How will you manage any ethical issues?
5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?
6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?
7. How will you manage access and security?
8. Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?
9. What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?
10. How will you share the data?
11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

¹ http://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/resource/DMP/DMP_Checklist_2013.pdf

12. Who will be responsible for data management?
13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

The preparation of the present deliverable has consisted in answering all these questions.

The remainder of the document D1.8 is organised as follows:

- **Chapter 1:** Introduction
- **Chapter 2:** Policy on scientific publications
- **Chapter 3:** Data management methodology used in the HIT2GAP project
- **Chapter 4:** Data set reference, name and description. The data sets tables that will be used within the project and that will be updated across the project lifespan.
- **Chapter 5:** Conclusions

Data Management Plan activities are conducted as part of WP1 and are also related to the task 1.2 related to the specifications of the field data infrastructure. The DMP is also closely related to the pilot sites where the data are collected and post-processed using the tools developed as part of the project. The partners involved in these activities are the one who collect personal data, and the pilot site managers as well as partners involved in the technical solutions associated to the technical data collection. Partners involved in the modules development and integration are also involved in the DMP as end-users of these collected data and as providers/generators of new data. The Task 7.3 (Scientific diffusion) leader, which is NUIG, is also involved in the DMP focusing on publications. The DMP is also consistent with and builds upon Clause 29 of the Grant Agreement related to Open Access.

1.2 Contributions of partners

NOBATEK has structured the work in this report, made a literature survey in the domain of Data Management and coordinated the collection of the input from the other partners involved in the data management plan within the HIT2GAP project. Pilot sites managers and developers of the modules related with post-processing of data have been involved in the process as well in order to collect their point of view and agreement or not on the openness of the data collected or generated. NUIG has set up and maintained the public repository used for the publications and data generated within the project.

1.3 Baseline definitions and concepts

The baseline document for **data management** in H2020 is “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0, 26 July 2016” [1]. As stated in this document, every participant to the **pilot action on open access to research data** should develop a Data Management Plan (DMP) in which they specify what data will be open, how it will be treated and managed. According to these guidelines, a DMP should be developed and detail:

- What data the project will collect and generate;
- Whether, and how this data will be exploited or shared and made accessible/open for verification and re-use;

- How this data will be curated and preserved.

The baseline document for **Open Access** in H2020 is “Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 [2].” According to this document, Open access is defined as follows:

*“**Open access (OA)** can be defined as the practice of providing on-line access to **scientific information** that is free of charge to the end-user and that is re-usable. 'Scientific' refers to all academic disciplines; in the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can refer to (i) peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals) or (ii) research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).*

These definitions describe 'access' in the context of open access as including not only basic elements such as the right to read, download and print, but also the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl, and mine.”

In relation to the HIT2GAP project, these concepts are applied in the following way:

- 1) HIT2GAP is mandated to provide an Open Access to its scientific publications: this is achieved by publishing research results in open access mode and making them available by uploading and indexing them to open access repositories (repositories indexed in the aggregator OpenAire (www.openaire.eu)). More precisely publications are available in the public repository [ZENODO](https://zenodo.org/communities/hit2gap/), in a special section for the HIT2GAP project following this link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/hit2gap/>. Additionally, links are provided in the HIT2GAP web page and partners are encouraged to disseminate results through more popular web-based platforms (e.g.: www.researchgate.net or www.academia.org);
- 2) HIT2GAP defines a data management plan compliant with the need to provide an open access to some of the other data collected and generated in the project.

2 Policy on scientific publications

With respect to publications, the following options are available:

- Publications are published in **open access** journals. This option is encouraged to all project partners. This means the journal grants open access by definition. These are normally:
 - Conference proceedings (IBPSA, CIBSE Technical Symposium, etc.);
 - Open access journals like ITCon (<http://www.itcon.org/about>) with no Article Processing Charges (APC);
 - Open access journals like Cogent Engineering with "low cost" APCs (<https://www.cogentoa.com/journal/engineering>) by Taylor&Francis.
- Publications are published in **gold open access mode**, that means a higher fee is paid and the publication is granted open access immediately;
- Publication are published in **green open access** mode, that means the publication can be made available after an embargo period, which is set up by the publisher. The publication fee is lower that the gold mode. The embargo period is substantially set for a longer period (18 months, 24 months etc.) than what is required under H2020 (6 months), so this option is not likely to be possible for H2020 so for the journals targeted by the project partners;
- Publications are **not published in open access** mode. This option is not encouraged.

In relation to the HIT2GAP project, these concepts are applied in the following way:

- HIT2GAP has made mandatory for all partners to provide Open Access to their scientific publications and data: this is done by granting open access to publications and data and uploading them to an open access repository;
- For HIT2GAP participants, the default open repository to upload scientific dissemination publications and datasets is ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org>);
- HIT2GAP is a "community" within ZENODO where all HIT2GAP papers are linked (<https://zenodo.org/communities/hit2gap/about/t>). Publications and data uploaded in ZENODO are indexed automatically in the OpenAire aggregator;
- Additionally, project partners might want to use other platforms to upload data or publications. Repositories for data are available within the "re3data" registry (www.re3data.org) and OpenAire (www.openaire.eu). Project partners are encouraged to disseminate outputs also in web-based scientific social networks such as www.academia.org or www.researchgate.net;
- Guidelines have been specified to all participants in order to meet all open access obligations, to meet the Data Management Plan, and to avoid conflict of interest with other participants, as required by Art. 29 of the EU Grant Agreement.

HIT2GAP project participants pursue default open access publications and GOLD open access publication option in line with EU grant agreement policies. In cases where GOLD open access is not possible, participants share preprints and/or accepted manuscripts according with the journal policies.

Within the peer reviewed process related to deliverables submission, the peer reviewers consider the DMP requirements in the review of the documents and outline specific datasets that should be highlighted and treated in accordance with the methodology proposed in the present document.

Internal guidelines have been elaborated to give all project beneficiaries the description of the process retained for the data open access within the HIT2GAP project (see annex, section 8).

Table 1 provides the list of data identified as scientific publications in the HIT2GAP project, and the associated accessibility strategy.

Table 1: Data identified as scientific publications and associated accessibility strategy used within the HIT2GAP project

Type/Category	Initial Identification	Accessibility /Sharing Strategy
Peer reviewed publications	Journal and conference articles related to the developments conducted during the project and the results achieved thanks to these developments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Access
Non-Peer reviewed publications	Conference papers; Project presentations at different events (seminars both at national and European levels, workshops, stakeholder's meetings...); Technical journal contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Access
Data used in the publication of scientific productions	Data inputs and outputs for data processing modules in publications; Data stored in the core platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Access
Public information and communication materials related to the HIT2GAP project	Newsletters, leaflets, Brochures, Posters, Press Releases; Public Deliverables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Access
Non-public documents related to the project	Confidential project deliverables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidential to consortium partners

3 Data management methodology used in the HIT2GAP project

This chapter details the way the project management activities and project management structure are related to the data management activities. It also proposes a data categorisation for the data collected and generated through the project as well as the repository options that are selected per each category.

3.1 DMP Management structure

As the HIT2GAP project is focusing on added value delivered through advanced treatment of the data collected in a building, data management is underlying all the activities within the project and is therefore reflected in all the project management activities.

The following table summarizes the main contributors in DMP within the project and their role in DMP. In version 4 of D1.8, the list of contributors has been updated to reflect the involvement of R2M in the demonstration activities conducted in the Irish pilot site.

Table 2: DMP Management Structure

Member of the HIT2GAP consortium	Main role in the project	Role in Data Management Activities
NBK	Coordinator WP4 leader WP8 leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manages EMDESK platform; • Drafts GM, PMT and GA meeting agendas; • Appoints quality reviewers; • Overall responsible for project management; • Manipulates data in the frame of the platform developed as part of the project; • Ensures privacy and integrity of the data collected during the project; • Develops and manages data management plan; • Ensures that data management is part of project activities including dissemination, deliverables quality review and project meetings; • Coordinates with the dissemination management of the project (BRE); • Coordinates with the scientific diffusion manager (NUIG); • Conducts the ethics issues management of the project.
MOS, BES, GIR, CYL, WRS, TEK, R2M	MOS=WP5 leader and manager of the Polish pilot site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manages the link with the pilot sites and aggregates the information related to the pilot sites (in this frame data are related to building

Member of the HIT2GAP consortium	Main role in the project	Role in Data Management Activities
	<p>BES=manager of the French pilot site</p> <p>GIR=manager of the Spanish pilot site</p> <p>CYL=manager of the Irish pilot site</p> <p>R2M=manager of the demonstration in the Irish pilot site</p> <p>TEK=pilot manager within the PMT</p>	<p>design, data measured in the building during operation, data from end-users, data from building owners);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensures that the occupants of the pilot sites are aware of the HIT2GAP project objectives and agree in participating to the demonstration phase of the project; Are responsible for getting the ethical authorizations from the national authorities in charge of data protection in the countries of each pilot site; Publish data used by modules developers in an open access platform.
R2M, API	<p>API=Innovation manager</p> <p>R2M=WP6 leader</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifies and manages the exploitable results (with the support of consortium partners); Coordinates with the dissemination manager of the project (BRE).
BRE, R2M	<p>R2M=Communication manager</p> <p>BRE=WP7 leader</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defines and implements dissemination strategy and dissemination plan; Gathers the information related to communications conducted by all the partners; Uploads public deliverables on the website and as such oversees Open Access Publications and Data; Collaborates with the activities dedicated to innovation and exploitation (coordinates with R2M);
NUIG	<p>Task 7.3 leader</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manages publications and related data in the consortium: verifies satisfaction of the publication policy specified in the document.
<p>HIT2GAP consortium</p> <p>Each member of the consortium manipulating data</p>	<p>Data generation and management</p> <p>Communication and dissemination</p> <p>Exploitation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness and implementation of the DMP; Is responsible for informing the dissemination manager of publications or patents being published in the frame of HIT2GAP;

Member of the HIT2GAP consortium	Main role in the project	Role in Data Management Activities
in the frame of project activities	Assurance quality control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishes data used during the development phase of HIT2GAP modules in an open access platform.

3.2 Data management process

This version of the D1.8 document is the fourth version of the DMP updated after 48 months of project.

This document has been updated as progresses were made in the project in terms of generated results, definition of exploitation associated to these results, and publications delivered during the project. To achieve this, the coordinator along with the innovation manager and the dissemination manager ensure that data management is correctly addressed at all levels of the project (PMT level, WP level, task level, pilot site level...).

The Coordinator, along with the Innovation and Dissemination managers identify annually the datasets that are generated through deliverables or technical developments and which of them can be considered as Open Access. They conduct discussions with the partners responsible for the deliverables and for the datasets that are generated.

An updated status of the data management within HIT2GAP project is delivered as a reserved section in each periodic report and a dedicated section is added in each project management plan.

3.3 Categories of datasets

In the frame of the HIT2GAP project, several categories of data and datasets can be defined:

- **Reserved or private data:** these data are used by the primary users (i.e., data owners),
- **Accessible and confidential data:** these data are used by the consortium members,
- **Available and public data:** these data are made available for third party/public users.

These data can be sparse in their nature. In this way, they can be grouped in two families: information data (for instance reports, deliverables, questionnaires related to the requirements of the different partners...) and technical data (e.g. measurements, IFC files, data produced by partners...).

3.4 Repository options and selection

For each category identified in Section 3.3, a storage repository should be selected to store the data in a way consistent with their open nature or not.

- **Reserved or private data:** these data is primary stored by users within servers or dedicated services managed by the company or institution to which they belong. This type of data is out of scope of the HIT2GAP DMP. Examples of these data are emails, telephone numbers or private account numbers, IDs.

- **Accessible and confidential data:** This can be divided in two types:
- Data regarding the ongoing **project documentation** is being stored in the EMDESK platform². This is a paid secured service managed by the project Coordinator which has furnished each project beneficiary with a secured and controlled access to the platform. EMDESK will be used all along the project. After a period of 6 months after the end of the project, EMDESK accounts will be closed and the coordinator will keep copies of the most important data and files on his own servers.
- **Technical data** comprised by data collected in the pilot sites, data coming from the end-users and data generated by the HIT2GAP modules. The HIT2GAP system architecture provides two different methods to store data in the platform repository: a set of APIs that allows the end-user to store data directly to the platform or using Plat.One services to collect data from various sources, normalize them and push these data to the core platform. The data collected by Plat.One are stored into a platform database located at ABO Data offices. All data are collected via secured interface channel and are stored in an anonymous format. Data can be accessed only using secured API's that provides the necessary decryption services. The local repository is protected via two levels of firewall and actually is totally closed from external access. After data local storing is completed some specific services push the new data to the central platform repository. At the core platform level, the data are stored in a dedicated storage repository with reinforced security layers measures against external vulnerability. This is described in details in the deliverable D4.3 "A prototype of the platform (BMS-OS) including the global framework of the platform as well as the elementary modules". It should be noted that discussions are currently in progress to continue the use of the HIT2GAP solution on some of the pilot sites of the project.
- **Available and public data:** these data are made available on an Open Access repository, which is Zenodo³ by default for the HIT2GAP beneficiaries. HIT2GAP is a "community" within ZENODO where all HIT2GAP papers should be linked. (<https://zenodo.org/communities/hit2gap/about/>, (see Figure 1). Other repositories can be used by partners as far as they offer similar accessibility assets and answer the European Commission requirements. Once data are stored, they can be bound to the HIT2GAP project through the OpenAire⁴ platform. This includes all data used in the project if not protected by a confidentiality or security clause, ruled by protection of personal data, or any other clause that would conflict with the publication of data.

² <https://EMDESK.eu>

³ <http://zenodo.org>

⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

Figure 1: Zenodo "HIT2GAP" community

3.5 Lifecycle of the Data management

3.5.1 Dataset management template

The sequential management of the data generated or collected within HIT2GAP is organized as follows:

- The data are first identified and classified according to the three categories defined previously;
- The data are then prepared in order to fill in the H2020 data management template presented below in Table 3;
- The data is stored in its corresponding repository (cf. previous section);
- The storage is then managed on the long-term (implementation of back-up storage solutions, accessibility management, data destruction...);

Table 3: H2020 Dataset template

H2020 Dataset Management Template	
Data set reference and name	Identifies the data set to be produced
Data set description	Description of the data that will be generated or collected, its origin, nature and scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and reuse
Standards and metadata⁵	Reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline that govern data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing.
Data sharing	Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In deciding on data sharing, ethical considerations, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, and security-related aspects should be considered.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup):	Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.

3.5.2 Generalities on data workflow in the HIT2GAP platform

The data collected and generated that are described in the present document include the data collection used in the global workflow of the platform developed in the HIT2GAP project called BEMServer. Various aspects are to be described to contextualize these data. The Table 4 provides a technical classification of these data (i.e. data to be considered in the global workflow of BEMServer).

Table 4: Technical classification of collected and generated data

Type of data			Description
Collected data	Building-related	Dynamic	Various data are measured on-sites, related to the building's working. Typically, such data are extracted from a BMS, or transmitted directly by sensors/actuators. Such data can be temperatures, humidity levels, state of a window opening, etc.

⁵ **Metadata:** Metadata is “data about data” or “information about information.” It is an information layer assigned to publications or datasets that make them identifiable, linkable and searchable.

			Some measures are also performed through similar systems regarding the external weather conditions.
		Static	Static data such as the description of a building is also collected, through different methods, typically questionnaires, BIM files, drawings, operations & maintenance manuals, etc.
	Occupant-related	Dynamic	Data are measured through positioning systems, to obtain information about the global occupancy of specific zones in a building ⁶
		Static	A questionnaire is transmitted to the occupants on a voluntary basis to collect their satisfaction level regarding energy-related comfort in a building
Generated data	Short term analysis		<p>Predicted values for energy consumption, indoor temperatures, etc.</p> <p>Reports; Types of faults; Alerts; Source of error, etc.</p> <p>Recommandations, actions, user state, etc.</p>
	Building performance simulation		Simulated values; reports; models
	Visualization modules		NA

One should note that all the data presented in Table 4 are part of the data that are shared by the partners' modules in the frame of the HIT2GAP project. In this context, all these data are stored in the data storage solution implemented in the Core Platform BEMServer, and available as inputs for every partners' modules.

The way these data are managed within the different software bricks is addressed in the documents related to ethics issues management (D9.1 [3], D9.2 [4], D9.3 [5] and D9.4 [6]).

⁶ It should be noticed that the smartwatches (wearable devices) have not been retained for the demonstration in the HIT2GAP pilot sites. These devices were planned initially to be used to collect additional information for the BM module. A wearable device refers to an electronic technology or a computer that is incorporated into items of clothing and accessories during the realization of the daily tasks of a user inside the building (watch, wristband, chest straps). The Smartwatch with android Wear has been selected initially to be applied in HIT2GAP. Nevertheless, different iterations between the partner in charge of deploying this technology and the pilot site where it was planned to be installed led to the decision of not using this technology during the course of the project.

4 Data set reference, name and description

This section describes the data that are collected or generated during the HIT2GAP project and provides an identifier for the data set, its origin (in case it is collected), nature and scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication.

This section provides also some information about the way these data are managed (made accessible or not).

This section also provides the data management template that is used within the HIT2GAP project and lastly it gives the template filled in with information related to the data collected and generated in the frame of the project and identified during the whole project duration.

4.1 Collected data

Table 5 gives a macro-categorization of the different data that are collected

- On-site generated data collected and stored in the HIT2GAP platform;
- Data collected by the project partners in order to develop the project work.

Table 5: Data collected in the frame of the HIT2GAP project

Type/Category	Initial Identification	Accessibility /Sharing Strategy
Pilot data	Measurements conducted in the 4 pilot sites coming from BMS or other sources of measurement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open by default • Restrictions can be made based on agreement of each pilot site.
	Questionnaire responses related to technical information about the buildings that include technical design drawings, technical data about the systems installed in the buildings, pilot site baseline situation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open by default • Restrictions can be made based on agreement of each pilot site.
	Responses to the questionnaire submitted to the occupants of the pilot sites in order to collect their preferences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidential to consortium partners
Research and development data	Questionnaire responses related to needs and users' requirements	Open Access (the answers to the questionnaire have been uploaded on ZENODO, https://zenodo.org/record/401009#.WM_wb2_hCpo)
	Responses to the technical questionnaire submitted in order to collect the information related to the tools brought by each partner in the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidential to consortium partners

Market exploitation data	Exploitable results identified by each partner to feed the deliverable D6.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidential to consortium partners.
	Technical sheet for exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidential to consortium partners
	Survey about HIT2GAP platform exploitation/governing entity creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidential to consortium partners
	Costs/benefits analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidential to consortium partners

4.2 Generated data

Table 6 gives a macro-categorization of the data that are generated by the project.

Table 6: Technical data generated through the development and use of the tools developed within HIT2GAP

Type/Category	Initial Identification	Accessibility /Sharing Strategy
HIT2GAP internal data	Data models defined as part of the project for the development of the platform (WP1). Building Performance Dictionary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The HIT2GAP data model is published on Github, and can be accessed publicly: https://github.com/BRASSIERPascale/BEMOnt The data model and the dictionary can provide a set of metadata describing the HIT2GAP data.
	Code of the HIT2GAP core solution (BEMServer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BEMServer is licensed under the GNU Affero General Public License 3. As such it is a free open source software. The code is published here: https://github.com/HIT2GAP-EU-PROJECT/bemserver
	Code of the modules developed as part of the HIT2GAP project and open source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ESP-r: Open Source, free to use, available from https://www.strath.ac.uk/research/energysystemsresearchunit/applications/esp-r/ Calibro: https://www.strath.ac.uk/research/energysystemsresearchunit/applications/calibro/
HIT2GAP processed data	Pre-processed data of the pilots; Knowledge based (semantic level applied on the field level data)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> These data can be made open for the public based on agreement of each pilot site; BEMServer implements a secured access to the data stored, to ensure confidentiality on the data access. This is technically implemented through RBAC principles.
	Post-processed and visualised data Results of the simulations applied to the pilot sites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> These data are available through the public deliverables dedicated to the outcomes of the project (D5.3, D5.4) BEMServer implements a secured access to the data stored, to ensure confidentiality on the data access. This is technically implemented through RBAC principles.

4.3 Dataset management template

As previously stated, a DMP requires a data management template in order to clearly identify the considered dataset and provide a management procedure for each of them. The H2020 dataset management template provided in Table 3 has been customised for the HIT2GAP project needs.

The following table gives the data management template that is used in the frame of the HIT2GAP project.

Table 7: Data management template used in HIT2GAP

HIT2GAP Dataset Management Template	
WP / Task & Data Manager	
Dataset reference / name	
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	

4.4 Datasets identified within HIT2GAP

This section details the data management templates filled in for data which are collected and generated in the frame of the project and mentioned at the beginning of the present chapter (section 4.1 and 4.2). This part of the DMP is the main part that evolves during the lifespan of the project and is updated and developed in a dynamic manner.

4.4.1 Building-related: measurements

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Building-related measurements	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP5 / MOS, BES, GIR, CYL, R2M, WRS
Dataset reference / name	Measurements conducted in the 4 pilot sites coming from BMS or other sources of measurement (individual sensors) except from individual devices.
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Energy consumptions Water consumption Indoor comfort conditions Indoor temperature Indoor relative humidity External weather data Physical data of energy systems (air temperature after heat recovery, Supply air temperature, Hot water supply temperature, pressure, Heat flow...) Systems settings and system status (setpoints, schedules, windows position, alarms...)
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	These data are collected from the pilot sites through BMS installed in the building or from additional measurement devices that may be installed to make the data more complete and more accessible to the project. In general, the data set contains: - Timeseries as CSV files - Timeseries metadata (description, unit, type,...) as JSON file or excel file These data are used for calibration of the simulation models, and as an input of modules in the management

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Building-related measurements	
	level (forecasting, FDD, behaviour modelling, energy management system, and visualization modules)
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	<p>The data can be presented in CSV, XML or JSON format, or any other non-proprietary simple format for time-series data.</p> <p>They can also be stored in any data storage solution. In the HIT2GAP project, a HDF5 file format is used to store large time-series data.</p>
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	<p>Based on agreements received from the pilot sites managers, subsets of these data have been published and made open access on Zenodo.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For NUIG, the dataset consists of measured values from 2 different energy meters installed in the Alice Perry Building of the NUIG university in Galway, Ireland, which measure respectively: (1) the thermal energy for heating delivered to the distribution loop towards the heating radiators of the thermal zone of the west part of the building, where many offices, and some meeting rooms and lectures rooms are located (measuring time interval of 1 minute, from April 2018 to the end of February 2019); (2) electrical energy demand for the chillers serving the whole building (daily values, from January 2018 to the end of February 2019). The dataset also contains measured values of physical variables, states and operating conditions from a detailed layout of data-points installed in an air handling unit, in the outdoor environment and in the related served room, which is a lecture theatre in the Alice Perry Building of the NUIG university in Galway, Ireland. The data have been made available for the period from January 2018 to the end of February 2019, at the measuring time interval of 1 minute. The variables list, with their explanations and graphical schemes, is available as attachment. • For Challenger, the energy consumption data as well as weather conditions data have been published on Zenodo. The dataset consists of energy consumption and weather data collected continuously during a period of 29 months at Challenger building (France). Energy consumption data at 10 minutes intervals include:

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Building-related measurements	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Heating and cooling electrical consumption (indoor and outdoor comfort units) for the 8 zones in the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Lighting consumption for the 8 zones in the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Plug load consumption for the 8 zones in the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Sanitary consumption for the 8 zones in the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Blinds consumption for the 8 zones in the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Air handling unit consumption for the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Total electrical consumption for the South Triangle (kWh) ○ Thermal energy consumption for VRF (Variable refrigerant flow) units of the South Triangle (kWh) <p>Weather data include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Daily degree days (°C) ○ Hourly humidity (%) ○ Daily rain precipitation (mm) ○ Hourly direct and global radiation (J/cm²) ○ Daily sunshine hours (hrs) ○ Hourly temperature (°C) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For Nanogune, the dataset consists of measured values from all the energy meters installed in Nanogune building located in San Sebastian (Spain). These meters differentiate between the electricity consumption of the intensive production equipment (chillers, clean room, laboratories, etc.) and the one related to the rest of the installation (offices, lighting, common areas, etc.). They also reflect the thermal consumption data (cold and heat) of each area of Nanogune building. There are 79 meters in total: 58 of them are electric meters, 20 thermal meters (10 cold, 10 heat) and a gas meter. All the meters have a time step of 15 minutes, and the data set covers a period of 5 months.

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Building-related measurements	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Wilanow Town Hall, the dataset consists of measured values from energy meters installed in the Wilanów Town Hall (Warsaw, Poland) which measure: (1) the thermal Energy for heating for the whole building and thermal Energy for the 3rd floor of the building (demo area); (2) electrical energy demand for the chiller serving AHU NW1 and electrical energy consumption on the 3rd floor of the building (demo area). The dataset consists also of data related to the physical variables such as: (1) operating conditions in the conference rooms served by the AHU NW1 such as temperatures, CO₂ concentration and humidity (2) weather data.
<p>Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i></p>	<p>For the long-term storage, the data can be stored on a hard drive if needed.</p> <p>Published data will be stored for at least 4 years after the end of the project.</p>

4.4.2 Building-related: description

HIT2GAP Dataset Management - Building-related description	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP5 / MOS, BES, GIR, CYL, WRS, NUIG
Dataset reference / name	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire responses related to technical information about the buildings, technical design drawings, pilot site baseline situation BIM files
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Drawings Energy bills Descriptions of the systems installed in the buildings Building envelop information HVAC systems information Descriptions of Energy sources Heating/cooling set point Schedules Zones for heating Cooling regulations Lighting systems information Building control infrastructure Building occupants' information Location of the building
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The data contains the responses to the questionnaires sent by MOS to the pilot site managers at the beginning of the project. These data are used for the simulations of the energy performances of the pilots, as inputs of the fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) modules and the 3D visualization module. These data, when possible, are directly collected from a BIM file.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire: there are no specific standards applicable for these data sets. IFC is an open format for BIM files; IFC is a standard format that provides with an open and interoperable data schema for exchangeable BIM

HIT2GAP Dataset Management - Building-related description	
	<p>models. IFC is curated by the building smart organization (buildingsmart.org).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some other files are proprietary formats (dwg files for drawing etc.)
<p>Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i></p>	<p>The questionnaire answers are stored on EMDESK. Files are provided in pdf format or any other non-proprietary format.</p> <p>There are a variety of documents in different formats that contain extractable data and information about the buildings.</p> <p>IFC files are available in BEMServer as downloadable assets. The rest of information is managed on EMDESK and not available through the HIT2GAP API.</p> <p>These data are confidential to consortium partners.</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i></p>	<p>Project data produced by the partners involved are saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system, and on EMDESK.</p> <p>Data will be stored for at least 4 years after the end of the project.</p>

4.4.3 Users-related: measurements

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – User-related measurements	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP5 / MOS, BES, GIR, CYL, WRS WP3 / EGE, EUR, TEK
Dataset reference / name	Measurements conducted in the 4 pilot sites coming from positioning solutions.
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Buildings/Zones/Rooms occupancy
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	These data are collected from the pilot sites through specific systems: a positioning system, worn by occupants on a voluntary basis. Presented as time series data. These data are used for the modelling of behaviour.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	The data are presented in JSON format. In the HIT2GAP project, a HDF5 file format is used to store large time-series data.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	These data are confidential to consortium partners.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	In the frame of the project, these data are stored in a HDF5 solution which offers functionalities for backup. Data will be stored for at least 4 years after the end of the project.

4.4.4 Users-related: preferences

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – User-related preferences	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP5 / MOS, BES, GIR, CYL, WRS WP3 / EGE
Dataset reference / name	Responses to the questionnaire submitted to the occupants of the pilot sites in order to collect their preferences
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Workspace Comfort (air quality, temperature) measured through satisfaction level, perception Occupancy Features adjustment Preference Ambient factors
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The data contains the responses to the questionnaires prepared by EGE in order to develop occupant behaviour model. The answers are specific to the behaviour modelling module and hardly reusable.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	The questionnaire answers are confidential to the consortium. The files are provided in pdf format or any other non-proprietary format.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the pilots involved are saved by the partner responsible for this task (TEK). Data will be stored for at least 4 years after the end of the project.

4.4.5 Needs and users' requirements

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Needs and requirements of end-users	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP1 / NBK
Dataset reference / name	Questionnaire responses related to needs and users' requirements
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	BMS providers' needs Facility managers' needs System manufacturers' needs Exploitation and maintenance companies' needs Building owners' needs Building managers' needs Users' needs Energy performance and efficiency
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The dataset is composed of the records of the stakeholders' answers to the questionnaire/interview and the literature review. These data have been used to underpin the modules definition within WP1 as well as the services proposition in response to the market needs (WP6).
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	These data are fully open. The answers to the questionnaire have been uploaded on ZENODO, https://zenodo.org/record/401009#.WM_wb2_hCpo .
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the partners involved will be saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system.

4.4.6 Internal: description of partners' software in HIT2GAP project

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – description of partners' software	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP1 / API
Dataset reference / name	Questionnaire responses related to the tools brought by each partner in the project
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Modules/Algorithms/Data treatment tool/Forecasting tool/Fault Detection & Diagnosis tool/ Data collection tool / Visualisation tool/user behaviour tool/Energy management tool/3D model/End-user type/ use case/input data/output data
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The dataset is composed of the responses to template provided to the partners bringing an existing tool to the HIT2GAP project.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	The questionnaire answers are stored on EMDESK. The files are in pdf format. These data remain confidential to the consortium.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the partners involved can be saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system or the HIT2GAP storage based on each case.

4.4.7 Internal: Market exploitation data

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Market exploitation data	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP6 / R2M
Dataset reference / name	Exploitable results identified by the partners
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Exploitable results
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The dataset is composed of the list of exploitable results defined by each partner and the associated SWOT analysis.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	The deliverable D6.1 is aggregating the exploitable results defined by the partners. This is a confidential document. Therefore, these data remain confidential to the consortium.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the partners involved will be saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system.

4.4.8 Internal: Technical sheet for exploitation

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – technical sheet for exploitation	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP6 / R2M
Dataset reference / name	Technical sheet for exploitation
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Exploitation
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The dataset is composed of some characteristics of the developed modules (skills required by an operator to use the module, inputs, outputs...)
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	The deliverable D6.2 is aggregating the information collected through these technical sheets completed by the partners. This is a confidential document. Therefore, these data remain confidential to the consortium.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the partners involved will be saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system.

4.4.9 Internal: Survey about HIT2GAP platform exploitation/governing entity creation

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Survey about HIT2GAP platform exploitation/governing entity creation	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP6 / R2M
Dataset reference / name	Survey about HIT2GAP platform exploitation/governing entity creation
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Exploitation
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The dataset is composed of the partner' answers to a questionnaire aiming at defining their commitment in the future exploitation plan of the HIT2GAP solution and the definition of the governing entity
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	The deliverable D6.2 is detailing the strategy that will be retained for the exploitation of the HIT2GAP solution. This is a confidential document. Therefore, these data remain confidential to the consortium.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the partners involved will be saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system.

4.4.10 Internal: Costs/benefits analysis

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Costs/benefits analysis	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP6 / R2M
Dataset reference / name	Costs/benefits analysis
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Exploitation Costs benefits OPEX CAPEX
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	The dataset is composed of figures related with costs of the developed solutions that will be used in the exploitation activities of the project and first plan of business model of the HIT2GAP solution.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	There are no specific standards applicable for these data sets.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	The deliverable D6.2 is detailing the strategy that will be retained for the exploitation of the HIT2GAP solution. This is a confidential document. Therefore, these data remain confidential to the consortium.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	Project data produced by the partners involved will be saved and backed up on the specific partners' own backup system.

4.4.11 Data generated by modules

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Data generated by modules	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP5 / MOS, BES, GIR, CYL, WRS + modules providers
Dataset reference / name	Data generated by short-term analysis modules (FDD, forecasting, behaviour modelling), energy management module and simulation modules
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Predicted consumptions, temperatures Alerts Recommendations Simulated values Reports Improvement opportunities
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	These data are generated by partners' modules, based on inputs which are either user-related data, building-related data, or other generated data. Some data can be presented as time series data (forecasted data, simulated data); other data will be considered as Events. The amount of data can be massive depending on the frequency at which data are produced. These data are to be used by other modules (simulation modules, short-term analysis modules, or visualization modules)
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	Time-series and Event data are presented in a JSON format. These data are stored in the data storage of the Core Platform: as RDF triples or in the HDF5 solution depending on their nature.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	These data can be stored by the modules themselves. Some of them are also stored in BEMServer, and their access is secured and restricted. Some of the datasets generated by HIT2GAP modules have been published on Zenodo. For instance, the data generated by the ENERIT module (Energy Management module) during its running on three pilot sites of the HIT2GAP project

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Data generated by modules	
	(Challenger (France), Nanogune (Spain), Wilanow (Poland)) have been shared on ZENODO.
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i>	For the long-term storage, the data can be stored on a hard drive if needed. Published data will be stored for at least 4 years after the end of the project.

4.4.12 HIT2GAP Data model and associated ontology

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – HIT2GAP Data model	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP1, WP4 / LIU, NBK, EUR
Dataset reference / name	HIT2GAP Data model and associated ontology
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Ontology Building Infrastructure User Behavior Sensor network Power Systems Semantic Interoperability Heterogeneous data
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	<p>The data model has been defined in WP1 activities and refined during the progress made during the IT developments of the platform.</p> <p>The data model is a compilation of OWL and RDF files that formalize the knowledge representation of a building within a HIT2GAP instance. OWL and RDF files should be opened with adapted tools like Protégé.</p> <p>The associated dictionary is used by any module in order to connect and use the data delivered by the platform.</p>
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	IfcOwl Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) SOSA QUDT CIM / IEC 61790 IEC 61850-7-420
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ontology developed and used within the HIT2GAP project is published on Github, and can be accessed publicly: https://github.com/HIT2GAP-EU-PROJECT/BEMOnt. The Github repository also contains some online documentation, and links to more detailed public online documentation pages • An article has been published in relation with the Conference LDAC 2017: “OntoH2G: A semantic model to represent building infrastructure and occupant interactions”, Richard Chbeir, Yudith

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – HIT2GAP Data model	
	<p>Cardinale, Aitor Corchero, Pierre Bourreau, Khoulood Salameh, Nathalie Charbel, Lara Kallab, Chinnapong Angsuchotmetee, Gulben Calis, 5th Linked Data in Architecture and Construction Workshop, 2017, 15-15 Novembre 2017.</p> <p>This article is open access and available on ZENODO: https://zenodo.org/record/1193292#.XV-grOgza70.</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i></p>	<p>All the elements are stored on Github, which provides a versioning functionality, and is free of charge</p>

4.4.13 Code of the platform developed as part of the project

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Code of the platform developed as part of the project	
WP / Task / Data Manager	WP4 / NBK
Dataset reference / name	Code of the platform BEMServer developed as part of the project
Mandatory Metadata	European Union H2020 HIT2GAP GA680708
Dataset Specific Metadata <i>(keyword(s) that categorize data to make it linked/searchable)</i>	Code Software HIT2GAP Platform
Data set description <i>(data description, origin, nature, scale, if it underpins a publication, who useful to, existence of similar data, possibilities for reuse)</i>	<p>The dataset is composed of the code bricks and software corresponding with the following elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code of the Core Platform (main development), • Code of the Webportal used to integrate modules' frontends, • Code of the Open Weather Map client. • Code of the core services developed as external services (ex: cleansing services), • Code of the IFC reader module (used to import information from IFC files to the Core Platform). <p>Additionally, some documentation has been generated, mainly addressed to developers of client modules of the Core Platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online documentation of the Core Platform APIs • Documentation on integration.
Standards <i>(reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing)</i>	<p>No standard available but best or common practices exist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open source code can be stored and handled on Github (http://github.com) • Online documentation to be publicly open.
Data sharing <i>(how data will be shared, identification of repository, existence of embargo period if any, identification of software or tools necessary for reuse)</i>	<p>All the source code is available through Github: https://github.com/HIT2GAP-EU-PROJECT/bemserver.</p> <p>The Core Platform online documentation is available on any instance running. One is therefore available for the instance running the HIT2GAP project: https://h2g-platform-core.nobatek.com/api/v0/api-docs/redoc</p>

HIT2GAP Dataset Management – Code of the platform developed as part of the project	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IFC data reader: https://github.com/Nobatek/ifc-datareader • Open Weather Map client: https://github.com/Nobatek/openweathermap-client
<p>Archiving and preservation (storage/backup): <i>(procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, estimation of costs and how covered)</i></p>	<p>The storage procedure of every elements stored on Github are handled by administrators of the different Github repositories (NOBATEK/INEF4 development team for source code; HIT2GAP developers for the guidelines for integration).</p>

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has provided details about the data management plan implemented within the HIT2GAP project. This is the fourth and final version of the DMP delivered at the end of project.

The main contributors in the data management of the project have been identified and their roles have been defined in accordance with the management structure of the project.

Open access consideration has also been introduced in the document in relation to the data collected and generated as part of the HIT2GAP project. In this respect:

- Scientific publications and related datasets are published with an open access. The proposed methodology is:
 - To grant open access to all project results in the ways described in this document;
 - To upload publications and datasets in an open repository, Zenodo by default;
 - To reference publications and datasets with HIT2GAP in the OpenAire platform;
- Data are available under an open access whenever this choice is not in conflict with confidential, security or privacy clauses.
- Confidential datasets are internal to the consortium and are uploaded in the EMDESK platform by default;
- Private data are stored in local machines and are be shared within the consortium.

The list of datasets collected and generated within the HIT2GAP project has been updated.

In this final version of the document, the list of datasets and software made open access has been updated. A special attention has been put on using standard open access modes to the publication and data that are released.

Internal guidelines have been used during the whole project duration to give all project beneficiaries the description of the process retained for the data open access within the HIT2GAP project.

The innovation manager, communication manager and project coordinator has served as references for questions related to data management in HIT2GAP.

6 References

- [1] H2020 Programme - Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0, 26 July 2016. Available at http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf.
- [2] H2020 Programme - Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, Version 3.2, 21 March 2017. Available at http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf.
- [3] D9.1 “NEC-Requirement n°3”, HIT2GAP project, March 2017.
- [4] D9.2 “POPD – Requirement n°2”, HIT2GAP project, March 2017.
- [5] D9.3 “H – Requirement n°1”, HIT2GAP project, March 2017.
- [6] D9.4 “M – Requirement n°4”, HIT2GAP project, March 2017.

7 Glossary and acronyms

API	APINTECH
BES	Bouygues Energies & Services
BMS	Building Management System
BRE	Building Research Establishment
CC	Creative Commons
CYL	Cylon Controls
DM	Data management
DMP	Data Management Plan
EGE	Ege University
EUR	EURECAT
FISE	Fraunhofer ISE
GIR	Giroa
GM	General Meeting
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LIU	LIUPPA Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour
MOS	MOSTOSTAL
NBK	NOBATEK
NUIG	University of Galway
OA	Open Access
PMT	Project Management Team
TEK	IK4-Tekniker
WP	Work Package
WRS	City of Warsaw

8 Annex: Guidelines related with the process for open access data within HIT2GAP

8.1 H2020 Open Access policy

This document is aimed at clarifying H2020 policy on open access and diffusion of project results and dissemination activities. All project beneficiaries are obliged under the H2020 Grant Agreement (Art. 29.2) to ensure **open access** to all peer-reviewed scientific publications and (Art. 29.3) research data;

How to comply?

Compliance with this open access policy is achieved by:

1. Granting open access to publications and research data and;
2. Uploading publications and/or data to public repositories.

In addition, all partners need to consider that:

1. The costs associated with publications should be handled by the partner who generates the publications. These costs are eligible so they can be declared to the EC (for instance in relation with the dissemination budget). Partners are responsible for managing their own budget. Please keep in mind that the budget is not extensible.
2. All beneficiaries must give 45 days advance notice to other project beneficiaries about the intention of disseminating results (Art. 29.1);
3. All beneficiaries should contact HIT2GAP Task-7.3 (luismiquel.blanesrestoy@nuigalway.ie) prior to submitting your results in order follow the correct procedures and to centralize curation of all HIT2GAP repositories and HIT2GAP reporting activities;
4. All beneficiaries must include the following disclaimer in dissemination and publications: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 680708" in order to properly link them to H2020 HIT2GAP project in repositories.

8.2 Open Access Options

Regarding peer-reviewed journal publications the following options are available:

1. Publications are published in **open access** journals. This choice is encouraged to all project partners. This means the journal grants open access by definition, these are normally:
 - a. Conference proceedings (IBPSA, CIBSE Technical Symposium, etc.);
 - b. Open access journals like ITCon (<http://www.itcon.org/about>) with no Article Processing Charges (APC);

- c. Open access journals like Cogent Engineering with "low cost" APCs (<https://www.cogentoa.com/journal/engineering>) by Taylor&Francis
2. Publications are published in **gold open access mode**, that means a higher fee is paid for APCs and the publication is granted open access immediately;
3. Publication are published in **green open access mode**. That means the publication can be made available after an embargo period, which is set up by the publisher. The publication fee is lower that gold open access, or it might be funded by library subscription fees. For all the journals consulted, the embargo period is substantially for a longer period (18 months, 24 months etc.) than what is required under H2020 (6 months). Therefore, this option is not workable for H2020 projects;
4. Publications are **not published in open access mode**. This option is not encouraged.

8.3 Open access repositories

For HIT2GAP participants the default repository to upload scientific dissemination material, is [ZENODO](https://zenodo.org). HIT2GAP is a "community" within ZENODO where all HIT2GAP papers should be linked. (<https://zenodo.org/communities/hit2gap/about/>.)

Zenodo is repository for both scientific dissemination articles and research data. Please remember that all peer-reviewed participation in conferences need to be considered in this repository.

The repository works very straightforward; you can use your ORCID account ID or use an email to register as a user and upload a paper. An automatic Creative Commons license generator is provided.

Figure 2 - Zenodo "HIT2GAP" community

When uploading a publication, participants should fill in the “funder” and “communities” fields with “hit2gap” and “OpenAIRE” text so Zenodo can show look for the correct tag and index the publication to HIT2GAP. For best results please contact: luismiguel.blanesrestoy@nuigalway.ie.

8.4 Open source licensing options

The Creative Commons (CC) license is a convention to let share, distribute, modify and acknowledge your work free and openly as an alternative to complicated application of intellectual property rights. In order to apply CC, you just need to:

1. **Choose the CC license** most appropriated type using the license chooser [here](#). There are 7 types of licenses (combinations of 4 properties). The most appropriate one for most articles is the "Attributions-NoDerivs CC BY-ND". The different types of licenses can be consulted [here](#), with examples [here](#).
2. **Marking your work.** This can be done in a number of ways, from copying and pasting a disclaimer and logo, to embedding a piece of code in a web page. More details for good practice [here](#).

The [license](#) itself is a legal type of text organized by articles. There is also a friendlier short description ([Commons Deeds](#)), and an electronic machine readable version. The B2SHARE portal offers a [license selector](#) , but this is only a portal to share data.

Figure 3 – Creative Commons "Attributions-NoDerivs CC BY-ND" license

8.5 Resources

On EMDESK:

Document Manager: "EMDESK/Work/WP7.../H2020 Open Access Supporting Material"

Online:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/sites/horizon2020/files/FactSheet_Open_Access.pdf
